

STAGES OF TEACHING WRITING SKILL IN NIGERIAN JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL.

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Abstract

This paper examined the stages of teaching writing skill in Nigerian junior secondary schools. What writing entails, stages of writing, strategies such as imitating a model, spelling, etc were discussed. The paper recommended that students should try and get recommended textbooks as this will improve their writing skill; the Ministry of Education should recruit enough qualified teachers of English. It is also recommended that teachers should be allowed to attend seminars, conferences and workshops so as to brainstorm issues on writing.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, English language is one of the core subjects taught in schools. Also, a credit pass in English is one of the prerequisites for admission of students into any higher institution of learning. The ability of the individual students to listen, speak and read well will improve such student's writing skill.

Language as a means of communication has four skills- listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening and reading are regarded as receptive skills, while speaking and writing are called productive skills. Writing is the process of representing one's thought, ideas and feelings graphically and conventionally. It is considered as the most difficult of all the language skills because the writing process demands for the author's presence of mind in simultaneous thinking, organising and reading.

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For students in junior secondary schools to effectively communicate, they need imagination in conceiving an idea, transforming the idea to a composition and finally, producing a written text that will be interesting and exciting. The students therefore need to give the appropriate intellectual and emotional investment to their writing. The skill of writing even though a strenuous task can be adequately developed through practice.

Writing

Writing is the highest and the most complex of all the language skills. Babatunde (1998) affirmed the complexity of writing by saying that it is the most difficult, tasking and demanding on the part of the writer because writing calls for the writer's presence of mind in simultaneous thinking, organizing and writing. This implies that as a writer writes, he as well reads.

Writing as a skill emerges from the ability of the writer to identify the letters of the English alphabets, use them to form words and sentences. This explains why Saleman (2008) asserted that a good writer must possess good imagination, sense of creativity and must be an individual with high level of organization.

Saleman (2008) quoted Ogunsiji (2004) that writing involves putting the graphic symbols that represent a language one understands, so that others can read the graphic symbols if they know the language and the graphic representations.

Writing is a continuous process. Fashiku (2011) supported this view by explaining that it is called a continuous writing because it allows the writer to relate a personal experience of another person, to discuss an idea or contribute to on-going contemporary issues. The issue of writing demands are numerous and endless and that whatever the demand is, students in junior secondary schools are bound to use words joined together in the form of phrases, clauses, sentences and paragraphs; these sentences must conform with the grammar and context of the demand of the topic. Tenses are vital in writing; hence, the students must use the appropriate tenses of verbs.

In short, writing entails deep thinking, appropriate use of language, clear and logical organisation of thoughts. In writing, the students have to carefully choose words to be used and organize them logically, while creating the context. Any form of writing is identified by its features such as content, organization, expression, mechanics and the use of language. The types of writing include essay types, such as narrative, descriptive, argumentative and expository, articles, speech writing and letter writing.

Stages of Writing

Writing as a process is considered as a major task involving various stages. These stages are pre-writing, writing and re-writing. The three stages shall be discussed one after the other.

Pre-Writing Stage

The pre-writing stage is a stage that deals with all the activities of the writer before the commencement of the actual writing. Olanrewaju (2010) opined that the pre-writing stage entails decision on what to write, knowing your audience, choosing appropriate topic and organising the ideas on the chosen topic. She added that the aim of writing should be linked with topic of discussion and that the audience should be considered too. Thinking about the audience assists the writer to select what to say and how to logically present the ideas.

Writing Stage

The next stage is the writing stage which lends itself to the actual writing by structuring the text. Abdulsalam and Adeoti (2007) posited that this stage involves connecting words together in a particular way to bring about meaningful sentences so that repetition and redundancy can be prevented. It is at this stage that content, organisation, expression and mechanical accuracy are marked.

Re-Writing Stage

The last stage is the re-writing or editing stage. Oluwole (2009) revealed that the re-writing stage is a stage whereby a writer edits his or her write-up so as to make the write up meaningful and error free. One fact is certain that it is natural for students to make mistakes of punctuation, spelling, omission, tense, etc during the course of writing under stress. If students submit their write ups without editing or proof reading, such write ups will be marked down and in order to forestall this, students must make it a point of duty to always proof read and make necessary corrections on their papers before submission.

In a nut shell, students should always use the stages discussed as guide to effective writing.

Strategies for Teaching Writing at Junior Secondary School Level

The major reason for writing is to express ourselves to others either to affect their points of view by presenting ours, make them change their positions on certain issues or things, make others understand the processes of a research experiment or even convince them to take action on certain matters. When we write, we do so to achieve certain positive results. The aim of any writing depends on the strategies employed.

This paper presents some of the strategies that teachers of English can employ for effective writing.

What good pronunciation is to speech is what good spelling is to writing. Spelling in English is a complex thing because English is a language of many sources. Such sources have their diverse rules. Words change form (spelling) when the grammatical context changes as we have in the past tense and plural markers. Students are supposed to be taught that some of these changes in spelling are done by suffixation or the adding of a letter or more to the actual word at the final position. A suffix is employed to change a word by replacing, by dropping or by adding. E.g. to 'ies' in the following inflections "lady" "ladies", "baby" "babies" and when some

words end in letters that are silent, they are dropped, e.g. 'better', 'shaped'!

Copying is another strategy that can aid effective writing. Obanya, Dada, Ihenacho and Olowe (1981) posited that the teacher should write out sentences or stories within the student's level of language competence, age and experience. The students then simply copy out what is written. They also added that the teachers can draw up a list of several simple sentences dealing with situations that the students are familiar with where the teacher will leave a blank space here and there for the students to complete by themselves. For instance, "My mother's name is _____".

In the space provided above, the student fills in his/her mother's name.

I like singing

I like _____

In the space provided above, the student fills in what he or she likes, e.g. oranges, sweets, biscuit, dancing, drumming etc.

According to National Teachers' Institute (NTI) (2007), imitating a model or adapting a model passage is another strategy that can develop writing skill in students. The NTI asserted that the educator can guide the students on continuous writing by writing a working sample on narrative, descriptive, expository or argument on the chalkboard. The educator can use newspapers cuttings or cyclostyled copies of a writing related to any of the areas listed as a model. The educator can equally ask the students to emulate its organisation structure and style to write their own attempts; he can at the same time ask his students to re-write a passage to suit what the students are required to do and by so doing, students can change names of individuals or places in the course of their writing.

Conclusion

Writing is so critical a language skill that teachers can not afford to treat its development in students casually. Oyetunde and Muodumogo (1999) asserted that being able to express one self properly in writing is obviously a sign of an educated person.

Writing is normally done in narration or a collection of sentence types. The smooth running of any narration is endangered without proper punctuation and spelling. For instance, if there were no period. It would not be possible to differentiate one sentence from the other easily. In English, there are other punctuation marks that render writing lucid and grammatical. These marks include the comma, the colon, the semi-colon, the exclamation mark, the inverted commas, the brackets, the dashes, the hyphen and the question marks.

Recommendations

The teachers of English language should give room for students to provide facts themselves when writing reports on daily life activities on their own rather than treating writing as a separate entity not related to students' experiences and other class subjects and that they should sufficiently equip students to meet the literacy demands of the modern society.

Educators should also employ the appropriate teaching aids, use diverse teaching strategies and teach the basic pattern the students needed for information soughting. This will enable them come-off the habit of phobia when faced with writing assignment and make the classroom situation lively.

On the part of the students, they should try and get the recommended textbooks as this will aid their development in writing. They should ensure that they participate fully during writing exercises/practices in the class with interest and that they should be encouraged to read written articles, reports, listen to speeches, radio and television programmes so that their writing skill will improve.

The Ministry of Education should recruit enough qualified teachers of English and give room for their teachers to attend seminars, conferences and workshops organised for them (teachers of English) from time to time so as to brainstorm issues on writing.

The parents on their own should try to purchase the recommended textbooks and necessary materials for their wards. Parents should endeavour to give their wards enough time to practice writing at their various homes, go through their writings and correct them where necessary (Ajibade, 2011).

Abstract

Abstract content including references to research methods, sample size, and findings. Mentions 'Senior Secondary Students' and 'writing skills'.

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